

TO WHAT EXTENT DO THE GOODS PRODUCED IN UZBEKISTAN MEET THE REQUIREMENTS OF INTERNATIONAL MARKETING

Abdimannonov Avazbek Abdug'oppor o'g'li

avazbekabdumannonov@gmail.com

Faculty of International Economics and Management, University of World
Economy and Diplomacy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ANNOTATION: Uzbekistan is a country with a booming economy and has a variety of goods to offer the international market. The standards of international marketing are becoming increasingly demanding, requiring quality and efficiency. In order to comply with international standards, Uzbekistan must produce goods that meet certain requirements.

KEY WORDS: International standards, product, quality, safety, requirements of ISO, WTO, trade, investment, marketing, company, manufacturer.

The products made in Uzbekistan must meet international standards of quality and safety. This includes meeting the requirements of the European Union's RoHS Directive and the Global Food Safety Initiative. Products must also meet the requirements of global certification agencies, such as the Global Organic Textile Standard and the Forest Stewardship Council. Other important requirements include compliance with the World Trade Organization's Technical Barriers to Trade and Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures, as well as with the United Nations' Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the International Labor Organization's conventions on labor rights and working conditions.

There are several types of international certificates that Uzbekistan companies can obtain. The most common are ISO (International Organization for Standardization) certificates. This is an internationally recognized certificate that is typically awarded to companies that demonstrate high levels of quality and customer service. Other certificates that Uzbekistan companies can obtain include, but are not

limited to, Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP), Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP), and Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS).

Obtaining international certificates can be a challenge for Uzbekistan companies. The process typically involves a review of the company's products, facilities, and operations. An examination of documentation and records may also be required. The process can be lengthy and expensive, as there are typically fees associated with the process. Nonetheless, the benefits of having international certificates outweigh the costs. Uzbekistan companies that obtain international certificates will be better positioned to compete in global markets, as they can demonstrate their commitment to quality and customer service. Furthermore, the certificates can help Uzbekistan companies to build relationships with potential customers, as they will know that they are dealing with a legitimate and reliable business.

First, Uzbekistan must produce goods that are of a high quality. Quality assurance is a key part of international marketing and Uzbekistan must have systems in place to ensure that the goods they are producing are of an acceptable standard. This includes ensuring that the materials used in production are of a high quality, that the production process is well managed, and that the final product is free from defects. What is more, the country's Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations and Trade sets quality standards for the products manufactured domestically. All manufacturers in Uzbekistan must adhere to these standards, which include requirements for materials, design, packaging, and labeling. The quality standards also require that products meet environmental standards and use renewable energy sources where possible. Additionally, manufacturers are required to provide technical information about their products and ensure that they meet the requirements of the relevant safety regulations.

Second, Uzbekistan must produce goods that are timely and efficient. International marketing requires that goods are produced in a timely manner, to ensure that they are available when needed. Additionally, it is important that the

production process be efficient, so as to reduce costs and maximize profits. Uzbekistan must have well-managed production processes, with quality control procedures in place, and have efficient transportation systems to ensure timely delivery of the goods.

Third, Uzbekistan must produce goods that are cost effective. International marketing requires that companies offer the best value for money, in order to remain competitive in the global market. Uzbekistan must ensure that the costs associated with production, such as labor and materials, are kept to a minimum, in order to keep the prices of their products competitive. When it comes to the requirements for exports, in order to be accepted on the international market, products made in Uzbekistan must also meet certain export requirements. These include a valid export license, a certificate of origin, and a declaration of conformity. Additionally, all products must comply with the applicable export control regulations, such as the Wassenaar Arrangement and the Arms Export Control Act. Exporting products made in Uzbekistan also requires that all packaging materials, labels, and documents comply with the applicable international standards. Moreover, all products must be cleared for export through the country's customs authority.

Let's take two famous brand companies as examples to our readers and manufacturers, such as Coca cola and Samsung Electronics. Because, these two companies have faced with lots of problems and they covered all stages to be a brand. Coca Cola is one of the world's most recognizable brands, but how did it become the powerhouse it is today? The company has been around since 1886, when a Confederate colonel, John Pemberton, concocted the syrup that would become the company's signature product. Since then, Coca Cola has grown into an international behemoth, with billions of customers around the world.

The success of Coca Cola can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the company has always been at the forefront of marketing and advertising. Its iconic red-and-white logo is one of the most recognizable symbols in the world, and its marketing campaigns have been as iconic as the product itself. The company was

also one of the first to take advantage of new technology, quickly adapting to radio and television in order to reach a wider audience. In addition, Coca Cola has always placed a strong emphasis on the quality of its product. The company has invested heavily in research and development in order to ensure that its drinks taste great and meet the needs of customers. This has led to the creation of many new and innovative products, such as Diet Coke, Coca Cola Zero, and the recent launch of Coca Cola Life.

Finally, Coca Cola has also been successful in reaching out to a broad range of customers. The company has invested heavily in advertising campaigns that speak to a variety of audiences, including teenagers, young adults, and the elderly. This has helped the brand to expand beyond its classic core demographic of middle-aged, middle-class Americans.

The success of Coca Cola is undeniable, and there is no doubt that the company has done a great job of reaching out to customers and creating an iconic brand. Through its innovative marketing and commitment to quality, Coca Cola has become a brand that is known and loved around the world.

Samsung Electronics was founded in 1969 as a small trading company in Suwon, South Korea. In the beginning, the company mainly sold electronic and electrical components to other companies. But soon the company changed its focus and began to manufacture their own products. In the early 1980s, Samsung Electronics began to expand into the international market. In 1982, the company opened its first international office in New York. Later on, Samsung opened offices in London, Paris, and other cities around the world. This global expansion helped to not only bring the company's products to new markets, but also to create an international brand. In the 1990s, Samsung Electronics made a big push to become a brand name. The company invested in marketing campaigns and product design that was aimed at attracting customers. They also started using the slogan 'Everyone's Invited' to emphasize the company's commitment to the customer. At the same time, Samsung was investing in research and development to create products that were unique and

innovative. This included the development of their own operating system (Bada OS), their own line of consumer electronics (such as the Galaxy S series of phones), and the development of new technologies.

As Samsung's brand became more established, the company began to focus on meeting international standards. In order to remain competitive in a global market, Samsung had to meet certain international standards and regulations. This included standards for product safety, environmental protection, and quality assurance. In recent years, Samsung has also become certified by various international bodies such as ISO, RoHS, and the GS Mark. These certifications help to ensure that Samsung's products are safe, reliable, and of high quality.

Is Investing in Marketing and Design Profitable? It can be difficult to decide where to invest the limited resources of a company. One area that often gets overlooked is marketing and design. While marketing and design may seem like an unnecessary expense, it can be a powerful tool for making a company more successful and popular.

Marketing and design can have a huge impact on a company's brand and reputation. A well-designed logo, website, and product packaging can make a company look more professional and trustworthy. This can create a strong impression with customers and potential investors. One of the most important aspects of marketing and design is its ability to draw attention to a company and its products. An effective advertising campaign or eye-catching design can create demand for a product, even if it's unknown or unpopular. This can result in increased sales and profits for the company.

Investing in design and marketing also has the potential to save money in the long run. By creating a professional, attractive image, a company can avoid costly damage to its reputation if a product or service fails to meet expectations. It can also reduce the amount of money spent on customer acquisition and retention. Therefore, investing in marketing and design is often worth the cost. It can help a company create a strong, positive image and attract attention to its products and services. In

the long run, it can reduce costs, increase profits, and make a company more successful and popular.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan must produce goods that meet the requirements of international marketing in order to be successful in the global market. Uzbekistan must ensure that the goods they produce are of a high quality, are timely and efficient, and are cost effective. By meeting these requirements, Uzbekistan can become a successful participant in international markets. The products made in Uzbekistan need to meet the requirements of ISO in order to be successful and widely accepted in the global market. Many companies are unaware of these requirements and are not able to produce products that meet international standards. It is important to recognize the importance of these regulations and to ensure that the products made in the country are up to par with the international standards. ISO requirements make sure that the products which are produced in Uzbekistan meet the quality and safety standards set by the global market. This will help ensure that the products are able to gain global recognition and acceptance. Additionally, it will also help protect consumers and ensure that they are getting products which are safe and of high quality. Ultimately, it is essential that the products made in Uzbekistan meet the requirements of ISO in order to be successful both domestically and internationally. Meeting these requirements will help the country become competitive in the global market, as well as create higher quality products and protect consumers. Companies should familiarize themselves with the ISO standards and make sure that their products meet the requirements in order to gain global recognition

REFERENCES:

1. Constantine S. Katsikeas, Saeed Samiee, Marios Theodosiou (September 2006). Strategy fit and performance consequences of international marketing standardization. Volume 27, Issue 9. 867-890. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/smj.549>

2. G. M. Peter Swann (2 June 2010). International Standards and Trade. A Review of the Empirical Literature. No 97. 51p. Available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/trade/international-standards-and-trade_5kmdbg9xktwg-en
3. Qoziboyev O. Ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotlar qanday standartlarga javob berishi kerak, article. From web-site: <https://zarnews.uz/uz/post/ishlab-chiqarilayotgan-mahsulotlar-qanday-standartlarga-javob-berishi-kerak>
4. All information about Coca cola available at: <https://www.coca-colacompany.com/company/history>
5. All information about Samsung Electronics available at: https://www.samsung.com/uz_ru/
6. Jonathan Koppell. International Organization for Standardization. (p.289-293) information available at: https://books.google.co.uz/books?hl=ru&lr=&id=Ha9J2nPhuXIC&oi=fnd&pg=PA289&dq=related:20ct7P8wI0sJ:scholar.google.com/&ots=WCeocENM1g&sig=dSSyB8snVb4AOHcq3w6qWeupcZc&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false
7. Matthew Potoski and Elizabeth Elwakeil. International Organization for Standardization 14001 (p.295-301). Taken from web-site: https://books.google.co.uz/books?hl=ru&lr=&id=Ha9J2nPhuXIC&oi=fnd&pg=PA289&dq=related:20ct7P8wI0sJ:scholar.google.com/&ots=WCeocENM1g&sig=dSSyB8snVb4AOHcq3w6qWeupcZc&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false